

Four methods of insecticide application for control of rice stem borers

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Four methods of applying insecticides recommended for control of rice stem borers were compared. There were seven treatments and four replications in a randomized complete block design. Plots measuring 2.5 × 5.5 m were planted to variety RD1. Insecticides carbofuran 3% G, triazophos 5% G, FMC 35001 40% EC, and monocrotophos 56% WSC were broadcast, used as root soaking treatment, and applied as, seedbed and foliar spray.

Broadcast carbofuran and triazophos at 1 kg a.i./ha and foliar sprays of FMC 35001 and monocrotophos were highly effective (see table). Yields were

Comparison of 4 methods of insecticide application for control of rice stem borers at the Khonkaen Rice Experiment Station, Thailand, 1978.^a

Treatment	Insecticide	Deadhearts (%) ^b	Yield (t/ha)
Broadcast ^c	Triazophos 5% G	0.67 a	1.5 bc
Broadcast ^c	Carbofuran 3% G	0.87 a	3.0 a
Foliar spray ^d	FMC 35001 40% EC	3.56 a	2.6 ab
Foliar spray ^d	Monocrotophos 56% WSC	4.53 ab	2.2 abc
Root soak ^e	Carbofuran 3% G	10.83 bc	1.5 bc
Foliar spray ^f	Monocrotophos 56% WSC	11.29 bc	1.8 bc
Root soak ^g	Carbofuran 3% G	12.03 c	1.4 bc
Seedbed ^h	Carbofuran 3% G	13.18 c	1.7 bc
Control	—	13.32 c	1.1 c
Seedbed ⁱ	Carbofuran 3% G	15.21 c	1.0 c

^aIn a column any 2 means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^bCounted at 40 days after transplanting (DT). Percentage of deadhearts from other counts was too small to estimate.

^cApplied at 1 kg a.i./ha every 20, 40, and 60 DT.

^dSprayed at 1 kg a.i./ha every 20, 40, and 60 DT.

^eApplied at 10,000 ppm 2 days before transplanting (DBT).

^fSprayed twice at 1 kg a.i./ha when the infestation was more than 5%.

^gApplied at 5000 ppm 2 DBT.

^hApplied at 2 kg a.i./ha 20 days after seeding (DS).

ⁱApplied at 4 kg a.i./ha 20 DS.

lower where triazophos was broadcast. Foliar sprays of FMC 35001 and monocrotophos were more economical

than broadcast carbofuran. Root soaking and seedbed applications were not significantly different from the check. ■

Control of the rice bug by ultra-low-volume (ULV) spraying

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A water-based ULV spray of either gamma BHC or dichlorvos, applied once at flowering with a hand-held battery operated spinning disk sprayer, effectively reduced populations of the rice bug *Leptocorisa* sp. through the heading stage (see table). This reduction was not reflected in a significant gain in grain weight, number of grains per panicle, or a reduction in unfilled grains. But the significant reduction in the percentage of bug-damaged grains increased the quality of milled rice from grade two to one (as specified by the National Grains Authority of the Philippines).

By drifting fine, relatively uniform-sized droplets onto the crop, ULV spraying covers the panicles and foliage with a droplet density equivalent to the thorough wetting obtained with a knapsack sprayer. The volume rate of 8 liters is considerably less than the recommended 1,000 liters/ha.

Ultra-low-volume spraying of 2 insecticides against the rice bug *Leptocorisa* sp. on irrigated lowland rice; (variety, C4-63)^a, Batangas province, Philippines, 1978 wet season.

Treatment	Bugs ^b (no./m ²)			Damaged filled grains (%)
	2 DS	5 DS	10 DS	
Dichlorvos	1.1 a	0.5 a	0.0 a	0.6 a
Gamma BHC	1.3 a	0.5 a	0.3 ab	0.6 a
Control	3.4 b	2.2 b	0.9 b	2.3 b

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

^bSprayed at flowering at 500 g ai/ha at a volume rate of 8 liters with an ULVA 8 sprayer.

DS = days after spraying.

With the savings in labor and chemicals, ULV spraying may be a viable alternative to the knapsack sprayer, particularly for small-scale farmers who underdose by

using volume rates that are too low.

IRRI is exploring the practicality of using ULV against the rice whorl maggot, stem borer, and brown planthopper. ■

Ovicidal activity of foliar sprayed insecticides on brown planthopper eggs

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Insecticides that can control the brown planthopper (BPH) have a short residual activity. Thus control is poor on nymphs that hatch a few days after insecticidal application. Timing of application would be less critical if the insecticide could kill eggs in addition to nymphs and adults.

To determine the ovicidal activity of several insecticides, BPH adults were allowed to oviposit for 24 hours on 25- to 30-day-old Taichung Native 1, a susceptible rice variety. One day after oviposition the plants were sprayed with the test insecticides at 0.75 kg a.i./ha. In a second experiment, BPH adults were allowed to oviposit for 48 hours. One day after oviposition the plants were sprayed with candidate compounds at 0.25 or 0.75 kg a.i./ha. Nymphs were removed and counted daily. At 14 days after oviposition, plants were dissected